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Are Asymptomatic COVID-19 Patients Risky?

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that COVID-19 is transmitted from people who are about to start or have just started to have symptoms. However, patients who have not yet shown symptoms are not asymptomatic; they are described as presymptomatic. Asymptomatic COVID-19 patients are patients who are diagnosed with PCR or antibody positivity but do not show any clinical and radiological symptoms. The proportion of asymptomatic patients among overall COVID-19 patients is very low. Because these patients did not show symptoms other than general-purpose screening, PCR testing was not performed. It is unknown how many asymptomatic patients we know in society. However, there is no evidence that these patients, who are asymptomatic, that is, do not show any symptoms or signs until they recover, are a contagion agent. Although this issue is controversial, the information is not based on concrete evidence. As a result, concrete evidence that asymptomatic COVID-19 patients contract COVID-19 has not yet been shown, and the fact that these patients are a focus of infection has still not been clearly clarified., and public health implications associated with this enigmatic group.

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Dear Editor,

The silent transmission of SARS-CoV-2 by asymptomatic individuals has been a significant hurdle in the effective containment of the COVID-19 pandemic. While much attention has rightfully been given to symptomatic cases, the nuanced nature of asymptomatic carriers raises critical questions about their impact on community spread, the potential for severe outcomes, and the efficacy of public health measures. This article aims to comprehensively examine the existing literature and provide insights into the risks associated with asymptomatic COVID-19 patients.

Understanding the prevalence and transmission dynamics of asymptomatic carriers is essential for effective pandemic management. We review epidemiological studies that investigate the proportion of asymptomatic cases, the duration of viral shedding, and their contribution to community transmission.

Asymptomatic carriers present unique challenges to public health efforts. We analyze the effectiveness of testing strategies, contact tracing, and isolation measures in identifying and containing asymptomatic cases. Additionally, we assess the impact of asymptomatic individuals on vaccination campaigns and the potential for breakthrough infections.

Are asymptomatic COVID-19 patients risky? The answer lies in a nuanced understanding of their epidemiological significance, potential clinical implications, and the challenges they pose to public health strategies. By unraveling the mysteries surrounding asymptomatic carriers, we can refine our approaches to testing, contact tracing, and vaccination, ultimately enhancing our ability to control the spread of SARS-CoV-2 and mitigate the impact of the ongoing pandemic.

It is well known that COVID-19 is transmitted from people who are about to start or have just started to have symptoms. However, patients who have not yet shown symptoms are not asymptomatic; they are described as presymptomatic. Asymptomatic COVID-19 patients are patients who are diagnosed with PCR or antibody positivity but do not show any clinical and radiological symptoms (1-4).

The proportion of asymptomatic patients among overall COVID-19 patients is very low. Because these patients did not show symptoms other than general-purpose screening, PCR testing was not performed. It is unknown how many asymptomatic patients we know in society. However, there is no evidence that these patients, who are asymptomatic, that is, do not show any symptoms or signs until they recover, are a contagion agent. Although this issue is controversial, the information is not based on concrete evidence (1-4).

As a result, concrete evidence that asymptomatic COVID-19 patients contract COVID-19 has not yet been shown, and the fact that these patients are a focus of infection has still not been clearly clarified.

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